

Order of elemental analysis

*You can bring your samples (min 5 mg) to Sylvie (lab 07) on Mondays and Thursdays **between 9:30am and 11:00am***

Customer

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Sample

Sample name: MAG190	
Aspect / texture: white powder	
Molecular formula: C ₅₄ H ₄₄ N ₆ O ₂	Molar mass: 808.99
Used solvent: H ₂ O, EtOH, Et ₂ O	
Structure:	

Sample details

Is the sample harmful? (skin, lungs, toxic)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample light sensitive?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample electrostatic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample hygroscopic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Do you want your sample back?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Additional informations:		

Elemental analysis

Sample name: MAG190

Single determination

Double determination

C <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	N <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other elements:		

Results

Analysis number: 2022-09			
Sample name: MAG190			
Expected values:	C 80.17 %	H 5.48 %	N 10.39 %
Results:	C 79.52 % - %	H 5.49 % - %	N 9.98 % - %
Other elements:			
Remarks:			

Date/Visa operator
01.03.2022, Sylvie Mittelheisser